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Graduates in Science and Engineering Globally

Increased on average by 26.09% between 2013 and 2022 for the analyzed countries

The variable "Graduates in science and engineering, %" refers to the percentage of graduates in science and engineering out of the total number of graduates in a given time period, usually one year. This measure is used to assess the level of specialization and the ability of an education system to provide qualified professionals in the fields of natural sciences, mathematics, and engineering. "Graduates" indicate the number of individuals who have successfully completed a degree program (bachelor's, master's, or doctoral) in a specific area of study. "Science and Engineering" includes scientific disciplines (such as physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics) and engineering fields (such as civil, mechanical, electronic, and computer engineering). The "%" (percentage) expresses the number of science and engineering graduates as a proportion of the total number of graduates, multiplied by 100 to obtain a percentage value. This variable is significant for analyzing various aspects, including economic competitiveness, as a high percentage of science and engineering graduates can indicate a highly skilled workforce, essential for innovation and economic competitiveness of a country. It also reflects the effectiveness of educational policies in promoting STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) subjects and provides insights into future labor market trends, especially in technologically advanced and scientific sectors. By analyzing this variable, important conclusions can be drawn regarding the technological development, innovation capacity, and workforce preparedness of a nation or region.

Graduates in Science and Engineering Globally in 2022. The data for graduates in science and engineering in 2022 shows significant variation between countries, highlighting substantial differences in their ability to train professionals in these crucial fields for innovation and technological development. The country with the highest percentage of science and engineering graduates is Oman, with an impressive 100%. This result suggests a strong investment by the country in scientific and technical training, likely supported by targeted educational policies and a well-structured educational system to promote such disciplines. Iran and Malaysia follow closely, with 99.8% and 99.6%, respectively, also indicating a particular focus on STEM disciplines. These countries may have well-funded educational programs and incentives for students choosing to study in these fields, reflecting their economic development strategy based on technological and scientific innovation. Other countries with high percentages include Brunei (97.8%), Tunisia (97.5%), and Uzbekistan (92.9%). These data indicate that even in different regions, education in science and engineering is considered a priority to support economic development and address global technological challenges. Germany, with 89.1%, confirms its reputation as a center of technological and industrial excellence, thanks to a robust education system that supports research and innovation. Interesting positions also include Singapore (87.7%) and Mauritania (84.8%), two countries with very

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different economic and social contexts but both with a strong emphasis on scientific and engineering training. India, with 82%, reflects its growing importance as a global technology hub, thanks to a large number of STEM graduates fueling its IT sector and tech startups. In Europe, in addition to Germany, other countries such as Austria (71.4%), Serbia (71%), and Romania (66.3%) show good percentages of science and engineering graduates. This highlights a solid technical skill base necessary to support European industrial competitiveness. Countries like the United Kingdom (56.7%), France (55.5%), and Spain (38.3%) present more moderate percentages, which could suggest a need to further strengthen their educational policies and incentives to attract more students to STEM disciplines. Italy, with 44.6%, is in an intermediate position, indicating room for improvement to increase the number of graduates in these strategic areas. In the United States, the percentage of science and engineering graduates is 33%, a surprisingly low figure for a nation considered a world leader in technology and innovation. This could reflect a diversification of educational choices among students, but also a need to intensify efforts to promote STEM careers. At the end of the list, countries like Bangladesh (5.6%), Guatemala (0.9%), and Mozambique (0.2%) show extremely low percentages. This could be attributed to a combination of factors, including a lack of educational resources, inadequate infrastructure, and perhaps lower interest or awareness of the opportunities offered by careers in science and engineering. These data highlight the urgent need for interventions to improve access to STEM education and incentivize such studies as part of national development strategies. In summary, the data show a large disparity between countries in the percentage of science and engineering graduates. Countries with the highest percentages demonstrate a strong ability to train professionals in crucial sectors for innovation and economic growth. However, there are many countries, especially those with low percentages, that need significant improvements in their educational and training policies to compete effectively in the global knowledge-based economy. Promoting STEM education should be a priority for these countries, considering the importance of such skills in the modern world and their direct impact on technological and socioeconomic progress.

Graduates in Science and Engineering Globally from 2013 to 2022. Data on STEM graduates (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) from 2013 to 2022 shows significant variations between different countries, reflecting the internal dynamics of each nation and their educational and economic policies. Countries like Niger, Brunei Darussalam, Benin, and Uzbekistan have seen impressive increases, with Niger increasing its percentage by 200%, from 3.2% to 9.6%. Brunei Darussalam registered an increase of 173.18%, from 35.8% to 97.8%, indicating a strong investment in STEM disciplines and effective policies to attract students to these fields. Benin increased by 166.67%, and Uzbekistan by 153.83%, suggesting similar investments and educational strategies. Jordan and Cambodia also showed notable growth, respectively 140.07% and 137.95%, signaling an increasing focus on STEM education. Romania saw an increase of 131.82%, while Mauritius increased by 122.83%, reflecting the importance of these disciplines for economic and technological development. Germany nearly doubled its percentage of STEM graduates, with an increase of 96.26%, indicating a strong existing base and further improvements. Other European countries like Belarus and Croatia registered significant increases, with 85% more than in 2013, demonstrating a consistent commitment to technical disciplines. The United Arab Emirates and Azerbaijan also saw increases of over 85%, emphasizing their strategy of economic diversification and reduction of dependence on the oil sector. In Latin America, Brazil showed an increase of 80%, while in Africa, Zimbabwe saw an increase of 73.33%, indicating a positive trend in various regions of the world. However, not all countries showed positive increases. Thailand, which in 2013 had

100% of its graduates in STEM disciplines, saw a significant drop of 37.9%, falling to 62.1%. Guatemala and Mozambique registered the most dramatic declines, respectively 96.77% and 98.39%, suggesting serious problems in their educational policies or economic crises that have negatively impacted the education sector. Bangladesh saw a reduction of 73.58%, and Angola of 53.8%, reflecting possible economic and social difficulties that have hindered the promotion of STEM disciplines. Turkey and Luxembourg also saw significant declines, respectively 44.7% and 44.16%, indicating a decrease in interest or opportunities in scientific and technological fields. Middle Eastern countries like Qatar and Saudi Arabia registered decreases of 27% and 25.2%, respectively, despite efforts to diversify their economies. In Europe, Spain and Hungary saw declines of 13.54% and 21.01%, suggesting possible changes in educational policies or economic priorities. Even in North America, the United States showed only a modest increase of 29.92%, signaling a need for greater investments and incentives to promote STEM disciplines. The variations observed in STEM graduate data can be attributed to a combination of factors, including national educational policies, government investments in education, available career opportunities, and general economic conditions. Countries with significant increases have likely implemented effective strategies to attract and support students in STEM disciplines, improving educational infrastructure, offering scholarships and economic incentives, and promoting gender equality and inclusion. Conversely, countries with significant decreases may have faced economic challenges, reductions in educational investments, or changes in political priorities that have negatively impacted the promotion of STEM disciplines. It is evident that to increase the number of graduates in science and engineering disciplines, an integrated approach involving targeted economic policies, investments in education, and collaborations between the public and private sectors is essential. Only through a coordinated and sustained effort will it be possible to create a favorable environment for STEM education, ensuring sustainable economic growth and greater global competitiveness. Educational policies should include early orientation programs, improvement of school infrastructure, continuous training for teachers, and economic incentives for students. Additionally, promoting gender equality and inclusion in STEM disciplines, overcoming gender stereotypes, and ensuring that all students have equal opportunities for success is essential. Collaboration between educational institutions, companies, and research centers can foster the development of relevant study programs aligned with labor market needs, improving the quality of education and innovation. Investing in research and development, supporting innovative projects, and creating career opportunities in the scientific and technological sector are equally crucial for retaining talent and preventing brain drain. Finally, early awareness and orientation in schools can increase student interest in STEM disciplines, stimulating curiosity and enthusiasm for these subjects. Using media and communication campaigns to promote STEM careers and presenting successful role models can help change perception and increase the attractiveness of these career paths. Through these strategies, it is possible to create an educational ecosystem that supports the increase in the number of STEM graduates, ensuring a prosperous and innovative future for generations to come.

Economic Policies to Increase the Number of STEM Graduates. To increase the number of graduates in STEM disciplines (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), a series of targeted economic policies are necessary to incentivize and support students from primary school through university. A crucial first step is to increase funding for education, particularly for schools and universities that offer STEM programs. This funding can be used to improve educational infrastructure, provide equipped laboratories, update teaching technologies, and ensure access to modern teaching materials. Additionally, it is essential to improve the training and recruitment of science and technical subject teachers by offering them competitive salaries and opportunities for

continuous professional development. Another fundamental aspect concerns the introduction of scholarship programs and economic incentives for students who choose to pursue STEM studies. These incentives can include merit- and need-based scholarships, low-interest student loans, and even tax exemptions for students' families. Promoting gender equality in STEM disciplines is another key objective, and to achieve this, mentoring and support programs for female students could be implemented to overcome gender stereotypes and encourage them to pursue careers in these fields. Collaboration between the public and private sectors can also play a crucial role in strengthening STEM education. Companies can contribute through partnerships with schools and universities, offering internships, apprenticeships, and practical training programs that allow students to gain field experience. Such collaborations can also lead to the creation of more relevant and market-aligned study programs, ensuring that graduates are ready to contribute effectively once they complete their studies. Economic policies should also include investments in research and development, supporting projects that involve students and encourage them to actively participate in scientific innovations and discoveries. Creating an environment that values research and offers career opportunities in the scientific and technological sector is fundamental for retaining talent and preventing brain drain. Additionally, early awareness and orientation in schools are crucial to increasing student interest in STEM disciplines. Educational programs, science fairs, competitions, and extracurricular activities can help stimulate curiosity and enthusiasm for these subjects. Using media and communication campaigns to promote STEM careers and presenting successful role models can help change perception and increase the attractiveness of these professional paths. Finally, economic policies should include measures to ensure equitable access to STEM education for all segments of the population, regardless of socio-economic status, geographic location, or ethnicity. This could involve offering support programs for students from disadvantaged communities, reducing regional disparities in educational provision, and promoting an inclusive and diverse education system. All these combined strategies can create a favorable ecosystem for increasing the number of graduates in STEM disciplines, contributing to sustainable and innovative economic growth. The government can incentivize schools and universities to develop study programs that are flexible and adaptable to the rapid changes in the technological sector, ensuring that students are always up-to-date on the latest developments and have the skills necessary to face future challenges. In this context, the implementation of policies that promote continuous learning and professional retraining can help maintain a flexible workforce ready to adapt to market needs. Additionally, creating networks of collaboration between educational institutions, companies, and research centers can facilitate the exchange of knowledge and skills, improving the quality of education and innovation. Promoting a scientific and technological culture in society is equally important to create an environment that values and supports STEM careers. Public events, conferences, and television programs dedicated to science and technology can help spread knowledge and interest in these disciplines. Finally, it is crucial to continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the policies adopted, collecting data and feedback from students, educators, and companies to make timely improvements and adjustments. Only through a coordinated and sustained effort will it be possible to significantly increase the number of graduates in STEM disciplines, ensuring lasting economic growth and greater global competitiveness.

Conclusions. STEM graduates grew on average by 26.09% between 2013 and 2022, from 36.2 to 45.6 units in the analyzed countries. Some countries have seen much higher growth rates than the period average, such as Niger with +200.00%; Brunei Darussalam with +173.18%, Benin with +166.67%, Uzbekistan with +153.83%, and Jordan with +140.07%. There are also countries where the number of STEM graduates has significantly decreased between 2013 and 2022, such as Turkey with -44.7%, Angola with -53.8%, Bangladesh with -73.58%, Guatemala with -96.77%, and Mozambique with -98.39%. Looking at the distribution data for STEM graduates in 2022, some rather paradoxical results emerge. It is generally assumed that most countries with high per capita income tend to have a very high number of STEM graduates. However, many countries with middle-high per capita incomes have a STEM graduate rate of around 50%, such as France, Switzerland, Canada, and the United Kingdom. Even Japan, which is a technologically very advanced country, has a STEM graduate rate of around 34.5%. Paradoxically, one of the countries with a high level of STEM graduates is Iran with 99.8%, Tunisia with 97.5%, and Uzbekistan. Germany is the first Western country for the number of STEM graduates with a corresponding rate of approximately 89.10%.

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